

Catgut Acupuncture for Weight Loss: A Preliminary Systematic Review of Randomised Controlled Trials.

Edgar Freitas dos Reis¹, Patrícia Silva Soares¹, Susana Querido¹, Carla Gomes Ferreira¹, Manuela Borges Inácio¹, Rodolfo Costa Torres² .

¹ CHINARTE, Viana do Castelo, Portugal;

² IPTC – Research Department in Complementary Therapies, Portuguese Institute of Taiji and Qigong, Maia, Porto, Portugal;

³ Saúde Oriental, Casével, Santarém, Portugal.

* Correspondence: saude.oriental@therapist.net

Abstract

Background: The prevalence of obesity has been increasing globally due to an increasingly sedentary lifestyle and dietary changes. The shift in daily habits has been linked to an increased risk of developing conditions such as overweight, obesity, type 2 diabetes, and metabolic syndrome. Acupuncture, a non-pharmacological treatment from Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), has been gaining global attention. Catgut acupuncture, a form of acupuncture point embedding, involves implanting surgical threads into specific acupoints for continuous stimulation. This review aims to examine the efficacy of catgut acupuncture for weight loss.

Methods: A systematic search for randomised controlled trials (RCTs) was performed using the databases PubMed, EuropePMC, and SciELO. The search terms included "(catgut acupuncture) OR (catgut embedding) AND (weight loss) OR (obesity) AND ("randomized controlled trial")". Studies were included if they involved human participants with a diagnosis of overweight or obesity and were published in English, Chinese, Spanish, French, or Portuguese. They also needed to report on anthropometric and morphological outcomes such as BMI, body fat percentage, and weight.

Results: The search identified 195 records, of which 10 studies were included in the final review, with a total of 963 patients analysed. Study durations ranged from 6 to 24 weeks, with follow-ups of up to 24 weeks. The studies focused on various populations, including perimenopausal women, patients with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, and obese adults. Catgut acupuncture was used as a single intervention or combined with other treatments like dietary intervention, exercise education, or Chinese herbal medicine. The results consistently showed a positive effect on weight loss and obesity-related health markers, with active treatment groups demonstrating more pronounced improvements compared to control or sham groups. Catgut acupuncture was particularly effective in reducing weight, BMI, and waist circumference. Some studies also found that the treatment regulated biochemical pathways and improved metabolic markers such as triglycerides, HDL, insulin, and HOMA-IR levels. The beneficial effects, including reductions in body weight and BMI, were maintained during follow-up periods of up to 24 weeks, suggesting long-term effectiveness.

Conclusion: Based on the reviewed RCTs, catgut acupuncture shows promise as a therapeutic option for managing obesity. The findings indicate that it not only aids in weight loss but also addresses underlying metabolic dysfunctions. However, the heterogeneity of the included studies, small sample sizes, and a lack of detailed analysis of safety aspects highlight the need for further high-quality research to establish its efficacy and support its integration into clinical practice.

Keywords: Weight Loss; Obesity; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Catgut Acupuncture; Catgut Embedding.

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1. Introduction

An increasingly sedentary lifestyle poses a significant risk for the rising prevalence of obesity ¹. The shift in daily habits, often seen in modern societies, negatively impacts metabolic health. This is because a lack of physical activity, combined with higher consumption of food and alcohol, leads to a slowed metabolism ^{2,3}. These behavioural changes are closely linked to an increased risk of developing overweight, obesity, type 2 diabetes, and metabolic syndrome ³⁻⁵.

The escalating rates of obesity, particularly in industrialised nations, highlight a potential for a continued and dramatic rise in these numbers. This trend may increase the demand for medical treatments, including bariatric surgery ⁶. This issue is not limited to developed countries; it is a global problem that is often underestimated. The prevalence of overweight and obesity is also growing in developing countries. ⁷ Statistics show a concerning rise in global obesity, increasing by over 50% from 8.7% in 2000 to 13.1% in 2016 ⁸. This surge is so significant that it has been labelled the "21st-century epidemic" ⁹⁻¹¹. This global health crisis is further underscored by the fact that obesity has become a leading cause of premature death worldwide. Obesity-related conditions, such as ischemic heart disease and stroke, were responsible for as many as 15 million deaths in 2019 ¹².

Given the magnitude of this problem, there is a clear need for effective interventions to promote intentional weight loss. This requires developing and implementing more affordable and successful prevention and management strategies at both the clinical and community levels ¹³.

Acupuncture, a key component of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), is a non-pharmacological treatment that's garnering global attention from both patients and doctors ¹⁴. While it has been practised in China for thousands of years, acupuncture has been making its way to Western countries since the 16th century ¹⁵. The therapy involves inserting fine needles into specific points on the body, known as acupoints, based on the TCM principle of meridian theory ¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Central to TCM is the idea that health is not simply the absence of disease, but rather a state of balance in a person's *Qi*, or "vital energy" ^{19,20}. Despite its growing popularity, some people, including healthcare professionals, lack comprehensive information about acupuncture's various methods, effects, and safety considerations ²¹.

Over time, new methods have evolved from traditional acupuncture, such as herbal acupuncture, electroacupuncture, laser acupuncture, and acupuncture point embedding (or catgut acupuncture) ^{19,22,23}. The underlying principle of catgut acupuncture is the implantation of surgical threads or catgut into specific acupuncture points to provide continuous stimulation ²⁴.

Recent research has shown that catgut acupuncture can be used to treat a variety of conditions, including menopause, depression, obesity, and both acute and chronic pain ^{14,24,25}. Recognising the increasing interest in catgut embedding acupuncture, and the need for a comprehensive summary of its effects, this paper examines its efficacy for weight loss. The analysis will be based on a review of existing randomised controlled trials (RCTs) to provide a clear overview of the technique's effectiveness.

2. Methodology

2.1. Search Strategy

To find RCTs evaluating the effectiveness of catgut acupuncture for weight loss, a systematic search was conducted. The search strategy, which included the terms (catgut acupuncture) OR (catgut embedding) AND (weight loss) OR (obesity) AND ("randomized controlled trial"), was applied to several electronic databases. These databases included PubMed, EuropePMC, and SciELO, and the search covered all available records up to 8 July 2025.

2.2. Eligibility Criteria

This review included RCTs investigating the effect of catgut acupuncture for weight loss. Studies were considered for inclusion if they: (1) involved human participants with a diagnosis of overweight or obesity; (2) were published in English, Chinese, Spanish, French, or Portuguese; and (3) reported anthropometric and morphological outcomes related to the topic such as body-mass index (BMI), perimeters, ratios, body fat percentage, and weight. Studies involving animal subjects or lacking proper intervention were excluded.

3. Results

Database searches yielded 195 records. Following the removal of 20 duplicates, 175 records were subjected to screening. Subsequently, 163 records were excluded, as detailed in Figure 1. The full texts of the remaining 12 studies were retrieved for a comprehensive assessment. Ultimately, 10 studies fulfilled the inclusion criteria and were incorporated into the systematic review. The study selection process is further illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Article selection flowchart.

A total of 963 patients were analysed across the included studies²⁶⁻³⁵. The duration of these studies varied, ranging from 6 weeks^{28,29,35} to 24 weeks³³ and follow-ups up to 24 weeks³². The included studies primarily focused on a population of overweight or obese individuals, exploring various related conditions and specific subgroups. These sub-

groups were mainly regarding age and hormonal status (perimenopausal women ²⁶), specific clinical conditions (Polycystic Ovary Syndrome with infertility ³⁴), co-morbidity status (with and without metabolic syndrome ³⁵), and general categories by gender (women ^{28,29}) or overall (overweight and obese adults ^{27,30-33}).

Moreover, several studies focused on acupuncture catgut as a single intervention methodology ^{27,28,30}, while some combined acupuncture catgut with dietary intervention ^{26,31}, dietary intervention and exercise education/orientation ^{32,33}, with moxibustion ³⁵ or moxibustion plus weight reduction program ²⁹, and with Chinese herbal medicine plus/or conventional medicine ³⁴.

Finally, comparators consisted of Sham acupuncture catgut or non-acupuncture point catgut ^{27,28,30,32,33}, electroacupuncture ³¹, sham acupuncture ^{29,35}, and Chinese herbal medicine plus conventional medicine ³⁴.

For a more detailed overview of the reported data, see Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the characteristics of the included studies.

Study	N	Duration	Population	Intervention	Comparator
Jin <i>et al.</i> ²⁶	84	8 weeks	Perimenopause women with central obesity	Catgut acupuncture treatment combined with dietary intervention	Sham catgut acupuncture treatment with dietary intervention
Xinghe <i>et al.</i> ²⁷	137	12 weeks + 4 weeks follow-up	Overweight adults	Catgut acupuncture treatment	Non-acupoints Sham catgut acupuncture treatment
Chen <i>et al.</i> ²⁸	90	6 weeks	Obese Women	Catgut acupuncture treatment	Sham catgut acupuncture treatment
Garcia-Vivas <i>et al.</i> ²⁹	37	6 weeks	Overweight/obese women	Catgut acupuncture treatment with moxibustion combined with a weight reduction program	Sham acupuncture
Yang <i>et al.</i> ³⁰	120	12 weeks + 12 week-follow-up	Obese adults	Catgut acupuncture treatment	Sham catgut acupuncture treatment
Notonegoro <i>et al.</i> ³¹	34	4 weeks	Obese patients	Catgut acupuncture treatment combined with dietary intervention	Electroacupuncture treatment combined with dietary intervention
Chen <i>et al.</i> ³²	216	16 weeks 24-week follow-up	Obese patients	Catgut acupuncture treatment combined with diet and exercise education	Sham catgut acupuncture treatment at sham acupoints combined with diet and exercise education
Dai <i>et al.</i> ³³	84	80 days + 12-week follow-up	Obese adults	Catgut acupuncture treatment combined with diet and exercise orientations	Sham catgut acupuncture treatment
Qin <i>et al.</i> ³⁴	62	12 weeks	Obese Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) patients with infertility	Catgut acupuncture treatment combined with traditional Chinese medicines + Clomiphene and HMG, and Duphaston.	Chinese medicine + Clomiphene and HMG, and Duphaston. Catgut acupuncture treatment + Clomiphene and HMG, and Duphaston.
Garcia-Vivas <i>et al.</i> ³⁵	99	6 weeks	Obese women without metabolic syndrome	The interventions included acupuncture with moxibustion, long needle acupuncture with moxibustion, electroacupuncture, electroacupuncture with moxibustion, and catgut acupuncture with moxibustion.	Sham acupuncture

4. Discussion

The main results of the included studies are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Major findings for each included study.

Study	Major findings
Jin <i>et al.</i> ²⁶	<p>Both the Catgut acupuncture treatment group and the control group experienced significant reductions in body weight, BMI, WC, HC, WHtR, and WHR after treatment (all $p < 0.01$).</p> <p>Specifically, the ACE group showed more pronounced improvements compared to the control group. For example, after treatment, the catgut acupuncture group had lower body weight and BMI values than the control group, indicating more effective weight loss ($p < 0.01$).</p> <p>The reductions in waist circumference and waist-to-height ratio were also greater in the catgut acupuncture group, highlighting a significant decrease in central obesity measures.</p>
Xinghe <i>et al.</i> ²⁷	<p>Both groups experienced significant WC reductions within 0-12 weeks ($p < 0.001$), with the catgut acupuncture group showing a more lasting effect during follow-up. After 12 weeks and at 16 weeks, the catgut acupuncture group maintained greater reductions compared to the control group, with statistical significance at 12 weeks ($p < 0.05$) and 16 weeks ($p < 0.05$).</p> <p>Body weight and BMI decreased significantly during the treatment and follow-up phases within each group ($p < 0.001$). The differences between groups were significant at 12 and 16 weeks, favouring the catgut acupuncture group, with p-values indicating stronger effects in the catgut acupuncture group (body weight and BMI reductions) during follow-up.</p> <p>Similar to other measures, HC showed significant decreases over the course of treatment and follow-up within groups ($p < 0.001$). Between groups, the catgut acupuncture group demonstrated better retention of reduction at week 16.</p> <p>Appetite VAS score: The score decreased significantly during treatment ($p < 0.001$) within both groups. The catgut acupuncture group showed a more sustained reduction during follow-up, with significant differences compared to the control group at weeks 12 and 16 ($p < 0.01$, $P < 0.001$).</p> <p>The rebound effect was observed after 4 weeks post-treatment, with some increases in these measures, but the catgut acupuncture group tended to have smaller rebounds compared to controls.</p>
Chen <i>et al.</i> ²⁸	<p>The catgut acupuncture group A showed a greater body weight reduction than the sham catgut acupuncture group B (-1.65kg vs. -0.38 kg, $p < 0.001$).</p> <p>BMI reduced from 30.7–3.9 kg/m² to 29.9 – 3.9 kg/m² ($p < 0.001$) in group A.</p> <p>Group A exhibited a greater WC reduction compared to group B (4.84 cm vs. 1.68 cm, $p = 0.04$). WC reduced from 96.6 – 10.2 cm to 91.7– 11.2cm ($p < 0.001$) in group A.</p> <p>HC was also significantly reduced in group A compared to group B.</p> <p>The trend of triglyceride also revealed a decline after catgut acupuncture group treatment.</p>
Garcia-Vivas <i>et al.</i> ²⁹	<p>The catgut acupuncture with moxibustion group significantly reduced weight and BMI.</p> <p>The catgut acupuncture with moxibustion treatment was associated with the regulation of biochemical pathways that are altered in obesity.</p> <p>The catgut acupuncture with moxibustion treatment did not modify circulating adipokine levels.</p> <p>After catgut acupuncture with moxibustion, leptin was negatively correlated with insulin, HOMA-IR, and adiponectin ($p < 0.05$). TNF-α was positively correlated with body weight ($p < 0.05$) and BMI ($p < 0.01$).</p>
Yang <i>et al.</i> ³⁰	<p>Both groups showed weight loss after the 12-week treatment, but the verum catgut acupuncture group experienced a significantly greater reduction compared to the sham group. The weight loss in the verum group was 2.8 kg, significantly higher than the 1.95 kg loss in the sham group.</p> <p>Both groups showed significant reductions in BMI after treatment, but there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups.</p> <p>Body fat in the verum group decreased during the whole process. There were no significant changes in body fat in the sham group after treatment.</p> <p>The waist, upper arm, and thigh girths in the verum group decreased significantly more than in the sham group.</p>
Notonegoro <i>et al.</i> ³¹	<p>Both the EA and catgut acupuncture groups showed a significant decrease in body weight after treatment ($p < 0.001$).</p> <p>The mean body weight decreased by 1.88 ± 1.43 kg in the EA group and by 1.47 ± 1.02 kg in the catgut acupuncture group.</p> <p>There was a significant decrease in WC in both groups after treatment ($p < 0.001$).</p>

The main result was a significant decrease in plasma-leptin concentrations in both the EA ($p = 0.012$) and catgut acupuncture groups ($p = 0.001$).

Comparison to control: There were no significant differences between the groups in weight loss ($p = 0.621$), WC ($p = 0.545$), and plasma-leptin concentration ($p = 0.784$).

Chen *et al.*³² WC reduction at 16 weeks: 8.80% in the catgut acupuncture group and 4.09% in the sham control group. The between-group difference was 4.71% ($p < 0.0001$).

WC reduction at 40 weeks: 8.46% in the catgut acupuncture group and 3.52% in the sham control group. The between-group difference was 4.94% ($p < 0.001$).

Weight reduction at 16 weeks: 7.92% with catgut acupuncture vs. 2.91% with placebo ($p < 0.001$).

BMI reduction at 16 weeks: 7.93% with catgut acupuncture vs. 3.06% with placebo ($p < 0.001$).

HC reduction at 16 weeks: 3.73% with catgut acupuncture vs. 1.88% with placebo ($p < 0.001$).

WHR reduction at 16 weeks: 4.97% with catgut acupuncture vs. 1.77% with placebo ($p < 0.001$).

PBF reduction at 16 weeks: 10.01% with catgut acupuncture vs. 5.01% with placebo ($p < 0.001$).

The group differences in weight, BMI, HC, WHR, and PBF remained statistically significant during the 24 weeks of follow-up ($P < 0.001$).

Dai *et al.*³³ The body-weight reduction in the catgut acupuncture group was significantly larger than in the sham control (net difference: 1.57 kg, 95% CI: 0.29–2.86, $p = 0.012$) from baseline to treatment endpoint. This persisted in the follow-up period (net difference: 3.20 kg, 95% CI: 1.17–5.21, $p = 0.001$).

BMI reduction was significantly higher in the catgut acupuncture group (net difference: 0.58 kg/m², 95% CI: 0.12–1.05, $p = 0.010$) after treatment. From baseline to follow-up endpoint, the net difference was 1.16 kg/m² (95% CI: 0.42–1.89, $p = 0.001$).

The mean change in WC in the catgut acupuncture group was more significant than SLAS ($p = 0.033$). HC showed no obvious difference ($p = 0.074$).

Catgut acupuncture significantly reduced SAT in L3-L4 compared with SLAS ($p = 0.043$), and significantly reduced the level of triglycerides ($p = 0.027$).

Qin *et al.*³⁴ The acupuncture-drug and catgut acupuncture groups showed significantly lower BMI and WHR compared to the Chinese medicine group ($p < 0.05$). There was no statistically significant difference between the acupuncture-drug and catgut acupuncture groups ($p > 0.05$).

Triglyceride levels significantly decreased in all three groups after treatment ($p < 0.05$). The acupuncture-drug group had significantly lower triglyceride levels compared to the Chinese medicine and catgut embedding groups ($p < 0.05$).

HDL levels significantly increased in all three groups after treatment ($P < 0.05$). The acupuncture-drug group had significantly higher HDL levels compared to the Chinese medicine and catgut embedding groups ($p < 0.05$).

Triglyceride levels decreased significantly only in the acupuncture-drug group ($P < 0.05$). After treatment, TC of the acupuncture-drug group was significantly lower than that of the Chinese medicine group and catgut embedding group ($p < 0.05$).

No significant difference was observed in LDL levels ($p > 0.05$).

FNS and HOMA-IR in the acupuncture-drug group were significantly reduced compared to those in the Chinese medicine and catgut embedding groups after treatment, whereas the HDL levels, periodic ovulation rate and clinical pregnancy rate were higher ($p < 0.05$).

Obesity treatment efficiency (weight loss) in the acupuncture-drug group and catgut embedding group was significantly better compared to the Chinese medicine group ($p < 0.05$).

Garcia-Vivas *et al.*³⁵ Body weight and BMI were significantly reduced in all treatment groups compared to the sham group.

No significant changes were observed in waist or hip circumference in any group at the end of the protocol.

Triglycerides were significantly reduced in EA, EAM, and catgut acupuncture groups.

Catgut acupuncture treatment led to a significant reduction in insulin and HOMA-IR. Catgut acupuncture was the only treatment to bring obese women back to a state of insulin sensitivity.

BMI – Body mass index, WC - waist circumference, HC - hip circumference, WHtR - waist-to-height ratio, WHR - waist-to-hip ratio, EA – Electroacupuncture, SAT - subcutaneous adipose tissue, TC - Total Cholesterol, LDL - Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol, HDL - High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol, HOMA-IR - Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance.

The results of the included studies demonstrate an overall positive effect of catgut acupuncture on weight loss and obesity-related health markers.

An important and consistent finding across studies is the superior efficacy of active acupuncture interventions compared to control or sham groups. While many studies showed that both treatment and control groups experienced some reductions in anthropometric measures, the improvements were consistently more pronounced in the active treatment groups. For example, in the study of Chen *et al.* ²⁸, the catgut acupuncture group's weight loss was more than four times that of the sham group (-1.65 kg vs. -0.38 kg). Similarly, in the study of Chen *et al.* ³², the catgut acupuncture group showed a 7.92% weight reduction, compared to just 2.91% in the placebo group, with these differences remaining significant even at the 24-week follow-up. This suggests that the therapeutic effects of these techniques are not solely due to the placebo effect or concurrent lifestyle interventions.

A key strength of these interventions is their targeted effect on central obesity. Multiple studies ^{26-28,32,33} reported significant reductions in waist circumference and waist-to-hip ratio in the active treatment groups. These findings are particularly relevant because central obesity is a major risk factor for cardiometabolic diseases. In some cases, such as the study of Garcia-Vivas *et al.* ³⁵, improvements in waist circumference were not significant across all groups, indicating that while effective for weight loss, the impact on specific anthropometric measures can vary depending on the exact technique used.

Beyond physical measurements, the data also point to the broader metabolic benefits of these treatments. Several studies ^{29,34,35} demonstrated that the interventions can regulate key biochemical pathways and markers associated with obesity. For example, catgut acupuncture with moxibustion ²⁹ was shown to regulate biochemical pathways and modify correlations between leptin, insulin, Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance levels, and adiponectin, as well as TNF- α with body weight and BMI. Moreover, the study of Qin *et al.* ³⁴ led to significant improvements in triglycerides and HDL levels, while the study of Garcia-Vivas *et al.* ³⁵ highlighted that the catgut acupuncture with moxibustion group was the only one to achieve a significant reduction in insulin and Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance levels, effectively restoring insulin sensitivity in obese women. These results suggest that the therapeutic effects extend beyond simple weight loss to address the underlying metabolic dysfunctions of obesity.

Several studies provided evidence of the long-term effectiveness of these treatments. The results from the study of Xinghe *et al.* ²⁷ and the study of Chen *et al.* ³² show that the beneficial effects, including reductions in body weight, BMI, and waist circumference, were not only maintained but also remained statistically significant during follow-up periods of up to 24 weeks. This suggests that these techniques may help mitigate the "rebound effect" often seen after weight loss interventions. Additionally, one study ²⁷ reported a sustained reduction in appetite in the catgut acupuncture group, which likely contributes to the long-term maintenance of weight loss.

Overall, these results are in concordance with several other studies systematically evaluating catgut acupuncture ³⁶⁻³⁸.

However, to strengthen the conclusions regarding catgut acupuncture's efficacy, several limitations must be addressed. The heterogeneity of participant characteristics, study durations, and intervention/comparator groups, coupled with relatively small sample sizes, is a critical issue that should be considered in future research. Furthermore, limitations within our study must be acknowledged. As a preliminary review, despite employing a systematic methodology, there are several aspects that could be improved upon in future studies. The number of databases searched should be expanded to ensure a more comprehensive literature review. Future systematic reviews should also include rigorous bias and quality assessments of the included studies. Additionally, a detailed analysis of methodological and safety aspects should be developed to provide a stronger evidence base and more validated conclusions. These improvements will be crucial for establishing a more robust understanding of catgut acupuncture's therapeutic potential.

5. Conclusion

Based on the analysed RCTs, catgut acupuncture appears to be a promising therapeutic option for obesity management. However, the identified limitations highlight the importance of conducting further research. Future high-quality research is essential to establish the efficacy of catgut acupuncture and to facilitate its potential integration into evidence-based clinical practice.

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References

1. Daniels NF, Burrin C, Chan T, Fusco F. A Systematic Review of the Impact of the First Year of COVID-19 on Obesity Risk Factors: A Pandemic Fueling a Pandemic? *Curr Dev Nutr.* 2022;6(4):nzac011. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdn/nzac011>
2. Amini H, Habibi S, Islamoglu AH, Isanejad E, Uz C, Daniyari H. COVID-19 pandemic-induced physical inactivity: the necessity of updating the Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030. *Environ Health Prev Med.* 2021;26(1):32. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-021-00955-z>
3. Medina C, Tolentino-Mayo L, Lopez-Ridaura R, Barquera S. Evidence of increasing sedentarism in Mexico City during the last decade: Sitting time prevalence, trends, and associations with obesity and diabetes. *PLoS one.* 2017;12(12):e0188518. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0188518>
4. Hu FB, Li TY, Colditz GA, Willett WC, Manson JE. Television watching and other sedentary behaviors in relation to risk of obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus in women. *JAMA.* 2003;289(14):1785-91. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.289.14.1785>
5. Wijndaele K, Duvigneaud N, Matton L, Duquet W, Delecluse C, Thomis M, et al. Sedentary behaviour, physical activity and a continuous metabolic syndrome risk score in adults. *Eur J Clin Nutr.* 2009;63(3):421-9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602944>
6. Zakka K, Chidambaram S, Mansour S, Mahawar K, Salminen P, Almino R, et al. SARS-CoV-2 and Obesity: "CoVesity"-a Pandemic Within a Pandemic. *Obes Surg.* 2021;31(4):1745-54. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11695-020-04919-0>
7. World Health Organization. Global strategy on diet, physical activity and health. 2004.
8. Collaboration NCDRF. Worldwide trends in body-mass index, underweight, overweight, and obesity from 1975 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 2416 population-based measurement studies in 128.9 million children, adolescents, and adults. *Lancet.* 2017;390(10113):2627-42. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32129-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32129-3)

9. Kramer H, Shoham D. The Millennial Physician and the Obesity Epidemic: A Tale of Sugar-Sweetened Beverages. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2019;14(1):4-6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2215/CJN.13851118>
10. Watson MC, Lloyd J. Obesity epidemic: bold and decisive action needed. *BMJ*. 2019;367:l6396. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.l6396>
11. Di Cesare M, Soric M, Bovet P, Miranda JJ, Bhutta Z, Stevens GA, et al. The epidemiological burden of obesity in childhood: a worldwide epidemic requiring urgent action. *BMC Med*. 2019;17(1):212. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-019-1449-8>
12. Park JH, Moon JH, Kim HJ, Kong MH, Oh YH. Sedentary Lifestyle: Overview of Updated Evidence of Potential Health Risks. *Korean J Fam Med*. 2020;41(6):365-73. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4082/kjfm.20.0165>
13. American Medical Association. *Is Obesity a Disease?*; 2013.
14. Van Hal M, Dydyk AM, Green MS. *Acupuncture*. StatPearls. StatPearls Publishing LLC; 2023.
15. Allen J, Mak SS, Begashaw M, Larkin J, Mlake-Lye I, Beroes-Severin J, et al. Use of Acupuncture for Adult Health Conditions, 2013 to 2021: A Systematic Review. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2022;5(11):e2243665. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.43665>
16. Silva H, Santos A, Monteiro A, Sousa IR, Rodrigues JM. Acupuncture for the Management of Breast Cancer: A Review of its Efficacy and Mechanisms. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura*. 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2025.100308>
17. Bernardo PS, Rodrigues JM. Acupuncture in acute COVID-19 treatment: A review of clinical evidence. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura*. 2024;18(2):100298. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2024.100298>
18. Simões K, Rodrigues JM. Acupuncture for erectile dysfunction: Insights and future research directions. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura*. 2023;17(4):100269. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2023.100269>
19. Rodrigues JM, Santos C, Ribeiro V, Silva A, Lopes L, Machado JP. Mental health benefits of traditional Chinese medicine – An umbrella review of meta-analyses. *Brain Behavior and Immunity Integrative*. 2023;2:100013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbii.2023.100013>
20. Matos LC, Machado JP, Monteiro FJ, Greten HJ. Understanding Traditional Chinese Medicine Therapeutics: An Overview of the Basics and Clinical Applications. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2021;9(3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9030257>
21. Wen J, Chen X, Yang Y, Liu J, Li E, Liu J, et al. Acupuncture Medical Therapy and its Underlying Mechanisms: A Systematic Review. *Am J Chin Med*. 2021;49(1):1-23. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0192415X21500014>
22. Kazemi AH, Adel-Mehraban MS, Jamali Dastjerdi M, Alipour R. A comprehensive practical review of acupoint embedding as a semi-permanent acupuncture: A mini review. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2024;103(23):e38314. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000038314>
23. Rodrigues JM, Ventura C, Abreu M, Santos C, Monte J, Machado JP, et al. Electro-Acupuncture Effects Measured by Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging-A Systematic Review of Randomized Clinical Trials. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2023;12(1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12010002>
24. Pei X, Song S, Li H, Lu D. Efficacy and safety of acupoint catgut embedding in treating postoperative pain of mixed hemorrhoids: A randomized controlled trial protocol. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2021;100(19):e25948. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000025948>
25. Li Q, Feng J, Zhang X, Zhao S, Kong M, Zheng Y, et al. Study on intestinal flora of acupoint catgut embedding intervention in female patients with abdominal obesity: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *TMR Integr Med*. 2022;6:e22010. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmr.2022.100010>
26. Jin Y, Huang Y, Zhu J, Liao D, Zeng S, Jin X. Acupoint catgut embedding regulates community structure of intestinal flora in central obesity during perimenopause. *Women Health*. 2024;64(10):857-69. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03630242.2024.2422876>
27. Xinghe Z, Qifu LI, Rong YI, Chonghui X, Yuhao J, Jiangqiong M, et al. Effect of catgut embedding at acupoints versus non-acupoints in abdominal obesity: a randomized clinical trial. *Journal of traditional Chinese medicine = Chung i tsa chih ying wen pan*. 2023;43(4):780-6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.19852/j.cnki.jtcm.20230608.002>

28. Chen IJ, Yeh YH, Hsu CH. Therapeutic Effect of Acupoint Catgut Embedding in Abdominally Obese Women: A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Study. *J Womens Health (Larchmt)*. 2018;27(6):782-90. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/jwh.2017.6542>
29. Garcia-Vivas JM, Galaviz-Hernandez C, Fernandez-Retana J, Pedroza-Torres A, Perez-Plasencia C, Lopez-Camarillo C, et al. Transcriptomic Profiling of Adipose Tissue in Obese Women in Response to Acupuncture Catgut Embedding Therapy with Moxibustion. *J Altern Complement Med*. 2016;22(8):658-68. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/acm.2015.0200>
30. Yang Q, Xu N, Guo L, Li H, Li X, Zeng Q, et al. Effect of acupoint catgut embedding for simple obesity in adults: A randomized controlled double-blind trial. *Integr Med Res*. 2025;14(2):101151. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imr.2025.101151>
31. Notonegoro C, Simadibrata C, Kresnawan T. Comparison of Therapeutic Effects Between Electroacupuncture and Thread-Embedded Acupuncture in Obese Patients Undergoing a Dietary Intervention. *Medical acupuncture*. 2022;34(6):380-90. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/acu.2022.0009>
32. Chen X, Huang W, Wei D, Zhao JP, Zhang W, Ding DG, et al. Effect of Acupoint Catgut Embedding for Middle-Aged Obesity: A Multicentre, Randomised, Sham-Controlled Trial. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM*. 2022;2022:4780019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4780019>
33. Dai L, Wang M, Zhang KP, Wang L, Zheng HM, Li CB, et al. Modified acupuncture therapy, long-term acupoint stimulation versus sham control for weight control: a multicenter, randomized controlled trial. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2022;13:952373. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2022.952373>
34. Qin W, Zhao K, Yang H. Effect of acupoint catgut embedding therapy combined with Chinese medicine for nourishing the kidneys and promoting blood circulation and improving blood glucose and lipid levels as well as the pregnancy rate in obese PCOS patients with infertility. *Exp Ther Med*. 2016;12(5):2909-14. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2016.3715>
35. Garcia-Vivas JM, Galaviz-Hernandez C, Becerril-Chavez F, Lozano-Rodriguez F, Zamorano-Carrillo A, Lopez-Camarillo C, et al. Acupoint catgut embedding therapy with moxibustion reduces the risk of diabetes in obese women. *J Res Med Sci*. 2014;19(7):610-6.
36. Zhao HY, Kim S, Son MJ. Comparing acupoint catgut embedding and acupuncture therapies for simple obesity: A protocol for systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2022;101(51):e31531. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/md.00000000000031531>
37. Jiali W, Lily L, Zhechao L, Jianping L, Mei H. Acupoint catgut embedding versus acupuncture for simple obesity: a systematic review and Meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of traditional Chinese medicine = Chung i tsa chih ying wen pan*. 2022;42(6):839-47. doi: <https://doi.org/10.19852/j.cnki.jtcm.2022.06.001>
38. Gao P, Xu X, Zhou M, Cui J, Yi T, Zhu T. The impact of acupuncture combined with acupoint catgut embedding on simple obesity: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2023;102(28):e34234. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000034234>